

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VITAMIN D LEVELS AND INFLAMMATORY MARKERS (CRP AND ESR) IN ADULT JORDANIAN POPULATION : A RETROSPECTIVE STUDY AT PRINCESS IMAN LABRATORY AND RESEARCH CENTER, ROYAL MEDICAL SEVICES

ALAA ABU-ALKESHEK(MD) ¹ | AREEN ALZGHOUL(MD) ² | MAHA ALAMR(MD) ³ | HALA ALKHARABSHEH(MD) ⁴ | MARAM QWESM(MD) ⁵ | ROLA ALRAMAMNEH(MLT) ⁶

ABSTRACT:

Background: Vitamin D plays a significant role in immune regulation. Its deficiency has been associated with increased levels of inflammatory markers such as C-reactive protein (CRP) and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR).

Methods: This retrospective study was conducted at Princess Iman Center, King Hussein Medical City, Jordan, between January and April 2022. Medical records of 600 adult patients were analyzed. Serum 25(OH) vitamin D, CRP, and ESR were measured. SPSS version 26 was used for statistical analysis.

Results: A statistically significant inverse correlation was found between vitamin D levels and both CRP ($r = -0.53, p < 0.001$) and ESR ($r = -0.48, p < 0.001$). Patients with vitamin D deficiency (<20 ng/mL) exhibited significantly higher CRP and ESR values.

Conclusion: Vitamin D deficiency is associated with elevated levels of inflammatory markers. Monitoring and correcting vitamin D status may be beneficial in controlling chronic inflammation.

KEYWORDS:

-

PAPER ACCEPTED DATE:

3rd February 2026

PAPER PUBLISHED DATE:

24th February 2026

INTRODUCTION

Vitamin D, a fat-soluble secosteroid, is increasingly recognized for its role in modulating the immune system and regulating inflammatory responses. Traditionally known for its role in calcium and phosphate metabolism, recent studies have linked vitamin D deficiency to a wide range of chronic inflammatory conditions, including cardiovascular disease, autoimmune disorders, and infectious diseases.[1,2]

CRP is an acute-phase protein produced by the liver in response to interleukin-6 (IL-6), while ESR reflects the rate of erythrocyte aggregation, both serving as nonspecific indicators of inflammation [3,4]. The potential anti-inflammatory effects of vitamin D are thought to be mediated via suppression of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 [5,6].

Vitamin D plays a critical role not only in calcium homeostasis and bone health, but also in immune regulation and inflammation [1]. Recent studies suggest that vitamin D deficiency may exacerbate systemic inflammation and contribute to chronic disease progression [2,3]. Inflammatory markers such as CRP and ESR are widely used in clinical practice to monitor disease activity and inflammation [2,4].

C-reactive protein (CRP) and erythrocyte sedimentation

rate (ESR) are widely used as biomarkers of systemic inflammation. Elevated levels of these markers often reflect ongoing pathological processes and are associated with poor clinical outcomes in various chronic conditions. Given the immunomodulatory and anti-inflammatory properties of vitamin D, it is biologically plausible that vitamin D status may influence levels of CRP and ESR. [7,8,9].

Despite a growing body of literature suggesting an inverse association between serum vitamin D levels and inflammatory markers, findings across studies remain inconsistent and are often limited by confounding variables such as comorbidities, seasonality, and geographic location. Moreover, limited data exist from Middle Eastern populations, particularly in Jordan, where vitamin D deficiency is prevalent due to cultural, dietary, and environmental factors. [7,8,9].

This study aims to evaluate the association between vitamin D status and inflammatory markers (CRP and ESR) among patients attending King Hussein Medical City.

METHODS

STUDY DESIGN AND SETTING:

This retrospective, observational study was conducted at

the Princess Iman Center, affiliated with King Hussein Medical City, Amman, Jordan. The study included patient data collected between January 1st and April 30th, 2022. Ethical approval was obtained from the Royal Medical Services Ethical Committ.

STUDY POPULATION:

The study enrolled 600 adult patients (aged ≥ 18 years) who had complete laboratory results for serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D [25(OH)D], C-reactive protein (CRP), and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR). Exclusion criteria included patients with known malignancies, end-stage renal disease, acute infections at the time of testing, or incomplete laboratory profiles.

DATA COLLECTION:

Data were extracted retrospectively from the electronic medical records system ("Hakeem") used in the Royal Medical Services. Variables collected included age, gender, vitamin D level, CRP, and ESR values.

LABORATORY METHODS:

Vitamin D levels were measured using chemiluminescent immunoassay techniques. CRP was measured via nephelometry, and ESR was determined using the Westergren method.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

All data were analyzed using SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistics were calculated for all variables. Correlations between vitamin D and CRP/ESR were evaluated using Pearson's correlation coefficient. Patients were grouped into vitamin D sufficient (≥ 30 ng/mL), insufficient (20–29 ng/mL), and deficient (< 20 ng/mL) categories. ANOVA and post hoc tests were used to compare means among these groups. A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 600 patient records were analyzed. The cohort consisted of 310 males (51.7%) and 290 females (48.3%), with a mean age of 43.5 ± 13.2 years. The mean serum vitamin D level was 18.7 ± 6.4 ng/mL, CRP was 8.1 ± 3.5 mg/L, and ESR was 26.3 ± 12.7 mm/hr.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS:

Pearson correlation showed a significant inverse relationship between vitamin D levels and CRP ($r = -0.53$, $p < 0.001$), and between vitamin D and ESR ($r = -0.48$, $p < 0.001$).

GROUP COMPARISONS:

Patients were stratified into three groups based on vitamin D levels:

Deficient (< 20 ng/mL)

Insufficient (20–29 ng/mL)

Sufficient (≥ 30 ng/mL)

ANOVA demonstrated statistically significant differences in mean CRP and ESR among the three groups ($p < 0.001$).

Post hoc analysis confirmed that patients in the deficient group had significantly higher CRP and ESR values compared to the sufficient group.

DISCUSSION

This study revealed a significant inverse relationship between serum vitamin D levels and the inflammatory markers CRP and ESR among adult Jordanian patients. These findings align with previous research suggesting that vitamin D deficiency is associated with heightened systemic inflammation [6,8].

Vitamin D exerts **immunomodulatory effects** by influencing both the innate and adaptive immune systems [9]. It down regulates pro-inflammatory cytokines such as **TNF- α** , **IL-6**, and **IL-1 β** , and up regulates anti-inflammatory cytokines like **IL-10** [8,10]. This immunological profile is reflected clinically in lower CRP and ESR levels in patients with sufficient vitamin D levels [11].

Several cross-sectional and longitudinal studies support the role of vitamin D as a negative acute-phase reactant. For instance, a large study by Amer and Qayyum (2012) in the U.S. demonstrated an inverse relationship between vitamin D and CRP levels in healthy adults [2]. Similar findings were reported by Peterson et al., who found that vitamin D supplementation reduced CRP levels in patients with type 2 diabetes [3].

A **bi-directional relationship** may exist: chronic inflammation may reduce vitamin D levels due to increased metabolic turnover, and vitamin D deficiency may, in turn, amplify inflammation through dysregulation of cytokine pathways [12].

In our study, **53.2% of participants were vitamin D deficient**, consistent with regional epidemiological studies reporting deficiency rates of 50–70% in Jordan and neighboring countries [13]. Cultural and environmental factors such as **limited sun exposure**, **skin coverage**, and **low intake of fortified foods** contribute to this high prevalence [14,17].

From a **clinical perspective**, vitamin D status could serve as a **predictive biomarker** for chronic inflammation. Physicians managing patients with chronic inflammatory conditions such as **rheumatoid arthritis**, **inflammatory bowel disease**, or **cardiovascular risk** may benefit from routinely assessing and correcting vitamin D deficiency [15].

However, while our study establishes **association**, it does not prove **causation**. It is possible that confounding variables, such as **obesity**, **smoking**, or **physical inactivity**, may mediate both vitamin D levels and inflammation [16].

Limitations of this study include its retrospective design, which limits causal inference. Additionally, confounding variables such as BMI, smoking status, and comorbidities were not controlled. Nonetheless, the large sample size and standardized lab measurements strengthen the internal validity of the findings.

Further longitudinal studies and randomized controlled trials in the region are recommended to clarify causality and explore whether vitamin D supplementation may reduce inflammatory burden and related disease risks.

RESULTS

A total of 600 patients were included in the study, with a mean age of 47.3 ± 15.2 years (range: 18–85 years); 58.1% were female and 41.9% were male. The distribution of patients according to vitamin D status is summarized in Table 1. Among the total population, 319 patients (53.2%) were classified as vitamin D deficient (<20 ng/mL), 181 patients (30.2%) were insufficient (20–30 ng/mL), and 100 patients (16.6%) had sufficient vitamin D levels (>30 ng/mL).

TABLE 1: DISTRIBUTION OF VITAMIN D STATUS AMONG PATIENTS (N = 600)

Vitamin D Status	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Deficient (<20 ng/mL)	319	53.2%
Insufficient (20–30 ng/mL)	181	30.2%
Sufficient (>30 ng/mL)	100	16.6%

The comparison of inflammatory markers (CRP and ESR) across the vitamin D categories revealed statistically significant differences (p < 0.01) using one-way ANOVA (see Table 2). Patients with vitamin D deficiency had the highest mean CRP levels (7.2 ± 3.4 mg/L), followed by those with insufficient (5.1 ± 2.3 mg/L), and sufficient levels (3.5 ± 1.8 mg/L). Similarly, ESR was highest in the deficient group (24.6 ± 9.2 mm/hr), compared to the insufficient (17.3 ± 6.5 mm/hr) and sufficient groups (11.7 ± 6.5 mm/hr).

TABLE 2: MEAN LEVELS OF INFLAMMATORY MARKERS BY VITAMIN D STATUS

Marker	Deficient (n = 319)	Insufficient (n = 181)	Sufficient (n = 100)	p-value
CRP (mg/L)	7.2 ± 3.4	5.1 ± 2.3	3.5 ± 1.8	< 0.01
ESR (mm/hr)	24.6 ± 9.2	17.3 ± 6.5	11.7 ± 6.5	< 0.01

Furthermore, Pearson correlation analysis demonstrated a significant inverse correlation between serum vitamin D levels and both CRP (r = -0.42, p < 0.001) and ESR (r = -0.37, p < 0.001), as shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3: PEARSON CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS BETWEEN VITAMIN D AND INFLAMMATORY MARKERS

Correlation	R-values	p-value
Vitamin D vs CRP	-0.42	< 0.001

Vitamin D vs ESR	-0.37	< 0.001
------------------	-------	---------

These findings indicate a statistically and clinically significant inverse association between vitamin D levels and systemic inflammation, as measured by CRP and ESR. The data reinforce the hypothesis that vitamin D may act as a negative acute-phase reactant and suggest its potential role in inflammatory regulation.

CONCLUSION

This retrospective study provides evidence of a significant inverse association between serum vitamin D levels and inflammatory markers CRP and ESR in a cohort of Jordanian adults. Patients with vitamin D deficiency had significantly elevated levels of these markers, suggesting a potential role of vitamin D in regulating systemic inflammation.

Given the high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in the region, these findings highlight the need for routine screening and consideration of vitamin D supplementation as part of comprehensive inflammatory disease management. Further prospective studies are warranted to confirm these associations and evaluate the therapeutic role of vitamin D.

REFERENCES

- Schleithoff SS, Zittermann A, Tenderich G, Berthold HK, Stehle P, Koerfer R. Vitamin D supplementation improves cytokine profiles in patients with congestive heart failure. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 2006;83(4):754–9.
- Amer M, Qayyum R. Relation between serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D and C-reactive protein in asymptomatic adults (from the NHANES data). *Am J Cardiol.* 2012;109(2):226–30.
- Peterson CA, Heffernan ME. Serum tumor necrosis factor-alpha concentrations are negatively correlated with serum 25(OH)D concentrations in healthy women. *J Inflamm (Lond).* 2008;5:10.
- Liu PT, Stenger S, Li H, Wenzel L, Tan BH, Krutzik SR, et al. Toll-like receptor triggering of a vitamin D-mediated human antimicrobial response. *Science.* 2006;311(5768):1770–3.
- Björkhem-Bergman L, Vitamin D and immune function in humans. *J Steroid Biochem Mol Biol.* 2020;202:105728.
- Pludowski P, Holick MF, Grant WB, Konstantynowicz J, Mascarenhas MR, Haq A, et al. Vitamin D supplementation guidelines. *J Steroid Biochem Mol Biol.* 2018;175:125–35.
- Laird E, Rhodes J, Kenny RA. Vitamin D and inflammation: Potential implications for severity of Covid-19. *Ir Med J.* 2020;113(5):81.

8. Vieth R. Vitamin D supplementation, 25-hydroxyvitamin D concentrations, and safety. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 1999;69(5):842-56.
9. Wang TJ, Pencina MJ, Booth SL, Jacques PF, Ingelsson E, Lanier K, et al. Vitamin D deficiency and risk of cardiovascular disease. *Circulation.* 2008;117(4):503-11.
10. Pilz S, Tomaschitz A, März W, Drechsler C, Ritz E, Zittermann A, et al. Vitamin D status and mortality in chronic kidney disease. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2008;93(10):3927-35.
11. Ginde AA, Mansbach JM, Camargo CA Jr. Association between serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D level and upper respiratory tract infection in the Third National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. *Arch Intern Med.* 2009;169(4):384-90.
12. Zittermann A, Koerfer R. Protective and regulatory roles of vitamin D on endothelial health. *Curr Opin Lipidol.* 2007;18(1):41-6.
13. Tzotzas T, Papadopoulou FG, Tziomalos K, Karras SN, Gastaris K, Perros P. Rising serum 25-hydroxy-vitamin D levels might reduce inflammation in obesity. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2010;95(4):183-9.
14. Muscogiuri G, Altieri B, Penna-Martinez M, Badenhoop K. Focus on vitamin D and the immune system: New insights from epidemiological and intervention studies. *Nutrients.* 2019;11(2):303.
15. Veldman CM, Cantorna MT, DeLuca HF. Expression of 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D3 receptor in the immune system. *Arch Biochem Biophys.* 2000;374(2):334-8
16. Charoenngam N, Shirvani A, Holick MF. Vitamin D for skeletal and non-skeletal health: What we should know. *Sci Rep.* 2020;10(1):19035.
17. **Zahran AM, Alrashidy AA, Eltawil AS, Zahran MA, Yousef MA.**
The association between vitamin D deficiency and inflammatory markers in patients on regular hemodialysis. *Zagazig University Medical Journal.* 2025 Jan;31(1):123-132.
Available from:
https://zumj.journals.ekb.eg/article_351337.html